

QUANTIFYING EFFICIENCY: ANALYZING COPING STRATEGIES AND OBSTACLES IN TEACHER PERFORMANCE AMONG PUBLIC SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Quantifying Efficiency: Analyzing Coping Strategies and Obstacles in Teacher Performance among Public School Teachers

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between coping strategies and perceived obstacles faced by teachers in achieving task mastery during the teaching and learning process. Utilizing data from surveys and assessments, the study explored how teachers utilized coping mechanisms such as Seeking Support, Active Planning, Disengagement, and Suppression of Competing Behavior to navigate challenges in educational settings. It also investigated various perceived obstacles, including time management, facility constraints, community support, student conduct management, and school leadership. The findings indicated that while teachers deployed coping strategies occasionally across different dimensions, they encountered occasional challenges in these areas. Despite these obstacles, teachers consistently demonstrated high effectiveness in their roles, as evidenced by performance evaluations. The study concluded by recommending targeted interventions and support systems to enhance coping strategies and mitigate perceived obstacles, thereby optimizing teacher performance and fostering a conducive learning environment.

Keywords: *coping strategies, obstacles, teaching and learning*

Introduction

Public school teachers encountered significant obstacles that adversely affected their ability to deliver effective education. Inadequate teacher training was a pervasive issue, with many educators lacking essential pedagogical skills and subject knowledge (Bozkuş, 2020). This deficiency often resulted in inconsistent teaching quality across classrooms, impacting student learning outcomes negatively. Despite efforts to implement professional development programs, the lack of sustained support and resources for teachers limited their capacity to adapt to new teaching methodologies and address the diverse needs of students effectively as highlighted by (Can et al., 2019; Can and Çağlar, 2017).

Research in different cultures globally stated that increased responsibilities for teachers do not always translate into a school's success. A study from the United States about workloads of teachers found that the average number of working hours of teachers is 54 per week (Kurt, 2022). Educators time with learners is limited, even if educators and administrators have an endless list of goals for them to achieve. But outside forces drive the educators to act as though the academe can handle everything through launching dozens of new projects, strive for exponential growth in each of the hundreds of testing standard, and provide students with thorough feedback on each prompt, assignment, and problem that made the teachers pressured and stressed.

Resource deficiencies further exacerbated challenges in teacher performance. Many public schools struggled with insufficient funding, leading to outdated textbooks, limited access to technology, and shortages of essential classroom supplies. These constraints forced teachers to make do with inadequate resources, hindering their ability to engage students in meaningful learning experiences. As a result, educators often faced difficulties in maintaining student interest and motivation, thereby impeding overall academic progress and exacerbating disparities in educational achievement among students from different socioeconomic backgrounds.

In the Philippines DepEd Negros Oriental Division deteriorating school infrastructure posed additional hurdles for public school teachers. Many facilities suffered from neglect, with poorly maintained buildings, overcrowded classrooms, and inadequate learning environments becoming commonplace (Nemenzo, 2018). These conditions not only compromised teacher morale but also created challenges in maintaining classroom discipline and fostering a conducive learning atmosphere. Teachers struggled to manage disruptive environments, detracting from their focus on instructional delivery and student engagement. The substandard conditions in which educators operated further underscored systemic issues within the public education system, highlighting the need for comprehensive reforms to support teacher effectiveness and improve overall educational outcomes (Go, 2017; David, 2018).

In Davao City, evaluation and accountability mechanisms in public schools often fell short of providing meaningful insights into teacher performance. Inconsistent evaluation criteria and lack of transparent feedback mechanisms limited the effectiveness of performance assessments. This ambiguity in evaluation processes led to disparities in recognizing and addressing areas for professional growth among teachers. Additionally, the absence of robust support systems for struggling educators hindered efforts to enhance teaching quality and student achievement. The inadequate oversight and accountability frameworks contributed to a cycle of stagnation in teacher development and educational improvement, perpetuating challenges in achieving equitable and high-quality education for all students in public schools (Evarado Jr, 2024).

Previous research has not adequately explored the collective impact of inadequate teacher training, resource deficiencies, deteriorating school infrastructure, and ineffective evaluation systems on teacher performance and student outcomes in public schools. Addressing these gaps was crucial for developing effective policies and interventions to support teachers, promote educational equity, and enhance

overall school effectiveness.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the impact of coping strategies and obstacles on teacher task mastery in the teaching and learning process. Specifically, this sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of coping strategies practiced by high school teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. seek support;
 - 1.2. active planning;
 - 1.3. disengagement; and
 - 1.4. suppression of competing behavior?
2. What is the extent of obstacles as perceived by the high school teachers?
 - 2.1. time;
 - 2.2. facilities and resources;
 - 2.3. community support and involvement;
 - 2.4. managing student conduct; and
 - 2.5. school leadership?
3. What is the level of teaching performance of the teachers in terms of IPCRF Rating?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the coping strategies and the performance of high school teachers?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the obstacles and the performance of high school teachers?

Methodology

Research Design

This quantitative study employed correlation to investigate causal-effect correlations, rather than an experiment. This correlational approach was used to explain the link between two specified variables, as well as to establish the direction and degree of the association itself. It was deemed reasonable to employ a descriptive correlation method to describe the existing state of affairs in order to study the reasons of a certain phenomenon. Correlational research aimed to identify correlations between two or more variables in the same population and examine their factual relationship. Two elements are measured rather than one, and this applies whether the factors are measurable or categorical (Curtis, Comiskey & Dempsey, 2016).

This survey gathered quantitative data to help describe the phenomena. The quantitative element of the study consisted of a well-planned data collection schedule that was targeted to the target audience's demands. Survey questionnaires were utilized to collect data for this investigation. The study's goal was to assess the extent to which earlier experiences and motivation influenced college students' participation. The correlational approach was used to measure two variables and assess the statistical relationship (correlation) between them, with or without any effort to adjust for other factors. It seeks to identify positive, negative, and zero correlations (Creswell & Creswell, 2017).

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 218 high school teachers of Monkayo West District. The study does not use sampling technique since the entire population will be the respondents of the study.

Table 1. *Respondents of the study*

School	Teacher-Respondents		
	Population	Respondents	Percentage
Awao National High School	19	19	8.6%
Casoon National High School	15	15	7.1%
Monkayo National High School	172	172	79.3%
New Kapatagan National High School	12	12	5%
Total	218	218	100%

Source: Monkayo West District Office

Table 1 shows the total number of teachers in each school and their corresponding sample and percentages. It shows that most respondents are from Monkayo National High School with 79.3% of the respondents. It is followed by Awao National High School with 8.6% of the respondents. Furthermore, Casoon National High School has 7.1% of the respondents. Lastly, New Kapatagan National High School has the least percentage with 5% of the respondents.

Instrument

In this study, the researcher used an adapted-modified survey questionnaire for Coping Strategies from "An investigation of coping strategies associated with job stress in teachers (Griffith et.al, 1999; Salimzadeh et.al, 2020). The set of questionnaires dealt with the level of coping strategies as perceived by high school teachers. The original questionnaire was modified to contextualize the school

setting. The original items were simplified or paraphrased to gain better understanding from the respondents. It was content validated by the panel of experts. It underwent the test of validity and reliability and was measured using Cronbach Alpha. For each item, the respondents were asked to rate the extent of coping strategies using the four-point Likert Scale anchored at (4) Always, (3) Frequent, (2) Rarely and (1) Never.

The second set of instrument embarks with the obstacles perceived by the high school teachers. It is an adapted-modified survey questionnaire from the 2022 North Carolina Teacher Working Conditions Survey (NCTWS, 2022). The set of questionnaires dealt with the different obstacles perceived by high school teachers. The original questionnaire was modified to contextualize the school setting. The original items were simplified or paraphrased to gain better understanding from the respondents. It was content validated by the panel of experts. It underwent the test of validity and reliability and was measured using Cronbach Alpha. For each item, the respondents were asked to rate the extent of coping strategies using the four-point Likert Scale anchored at (4) Always, (3) Frequent, (2) Rarely and (1) Never.

The third set of instrument embarks with teacher's task mastery among high school teachers. The research instrument for this variable was adopted from the nationally validated PPST-RPMS Tool as mandated by the Department of Education. For each item, the teachers will be rated in their level of mastery using the standard scale anchored at (5) Outstanding, (4) Very Satisfactory, (3) Satisfactory, (2) Unsatisfactory and (1) Poor.

Procedure

The following steps were taken into consideration by the researcher in the conduct of this study.

Permission. The researcher should make a letter asking permission to conduct the study to the Graduate School of Assumption College of Nabunturan, Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao de Oro and School Heads of the participating schools.

Data Collection. A survey questionnaire was administered to the teachers. IPCRF of each respondent asked from the school heads of the participating schools.

Interpretation of Data. Quantitative data were interpreted and analyzed using appropriate tools. The data will be presented in tabular form, interpreted and analyzed. The quantitative result will be thoroughly examined and analyzed by the statistician.

Interpretation of the results. The quantitative data will be analyzed using suitable data analysis. Weighted Mean and Pearson-r will be utilized as data analysis tool.

Data Analysis

Data analysis, formula for finding weighted means and Pearson-r will be used. Mean formula is used to identify the mean scores of the indicators in the survey questionnaire and PPST-RPMS Tool. In statistics, the Pearson's-r, the Pearson product – moment correlation coefficient or bivariate correlation, is a measure of the linear correlation between variables x and y and this tool was used to know the impact of coping strategies and obstacles to the task mastery of high school teachers. In all cases, the level of significance was 5%. Analysis of the data was done using SPSS student version.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Coping Strategies

Seeking Support. Table 2 shows the level of Coping Strategies in terms of Seeking Support.

Table 2. *The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Seeking Support*

<i>Items</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. I tried to get advice from colleagues.	3.3	Occasionally
2. I discuss feelings with others.	3.3	Occasionally
3. I talk to someone to find things out.	2.9	Occasionally
4. I get emotional support.	3.2	Occasionally
5. I get sympathy and understanding.	3.8	Frequently
Overall	3.3	Occasionally

Based on the Data provided items 1 and 2 got the same mean and quality index of occasionally. This was followed by item 3, which got the mean of mean of 2.9; item 4, which got the mean of 3.2 with the same quality index of occasionally; and finally, item 5, which got the mean of 3.8. The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Seeking Support got the overall mean of 3.3 with description of Occasionally.

Active Planning. Table 3 shows the level of Coping Strategies in terms of Active Planning.

Based on the data provided, items 1, 2, and 3 got the same mean of 2.8 with a description of Occasionally, respectively, followed by item 4 got a mean of 3.1, and item 5 got a mean of 3.2 with the same description of Occasionally. The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Active Planning got the overall mean of 2.9 with description of Occasionally.

Table 3. *The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Active Planning*

Items	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I concentrate to make efforts.	2.8	Occasionally
2. I make plan.	2.8	Occasionally
3. I take some actions.	2.8	Occasionally
4. I come up with strategies to handle things.	3.1	Occasionally
5. I do what has to be done.	3.2	Occasionally
Overall	2.9	Occasionally

From the data provided, we can see that items 1, 2, and 3 got the same mean of 2.8 with the same descriptive equivalent of occasionally, while item 4 got the mean of 3.3 and 3.2 for item 5 with the same descriptive equivalent of occasionally, respectively. The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Disengagement got an overall mean of 3.0 with a description of Occasionally.

Suppression of Competing Behavior. Table 5 shows the level of Coping Strategies in terms of Suppression of Competing Behavior.

Table 5. *The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Suppression of Competing Behavior*

Indicator	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. I prevent distractions.	2.8	Occasionally
2. I focus on what is necessary.	2.8	Occasionally
3. I prevent interference.	2.9	Occasionally
4. I concentrate on my wellness.	3.4	Occasionally
5. I stop trying attempts.	2.9	Occasionally
Overall	3.0	Occasionally

Based on the data provided, items 1 and 2 got the same mean while items 3 and 5 got also the same mean and got the overall descriptive equivalent of occasionally. The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Suppression of Competing Behavior got an overall mean of 3.0 with a description of Occasionally.

Obstacles as perceived by the high school teachers. Table 6 shows the Level of obstacles as perceived by the high school teachers in terms of Time.

Table 6. *The Level of Obstacles as Perceived by the High School Teachers in terms of Time*

Indicator	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Class sizes are reasonable such that teachers have the time available to meet the needs of all students.	2.8	Occasionally
2. Teachers have time available to collaborate with colleagues.	2.7	Occasionally
3. Teachers are allowed to focus on educating students with minimal interruptions.	2.9	Occasionally
4. The non-instructional time provided for teachers in my school is sufficient.	3.4	Occasionally
5. Teachers are protected from duties that interfere with their essential role of educating students.	3.0	Occasionally
Overall	3.0	Occasionally

Based on the ratings provided, items 4 got the highest mean of 3.4 while the item 5 got the mean of 3.0 it is followed by items 1 got the mean of 2.8; item 2 got mean of 2.7 and item 3 got the mean of 2.9 with same descriptions of occasionally respectively. The Level of obstacles as perceived by the high school teachers in terms of Time got the overall mean of 3.0 with the description occasionally.

Facilities and Resources. Table 7 shows the Level of obstacles as perceived by the high school teachers in terms of Facilities and Resources.

Table 7. *The Level of Obstacles as Perceived by the High School Teachers in terms of Facilities and Resources*

Indicator	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. Teachers have sufficient access to appropriate instructional materials.	2.8	Occasionally
2. Teachers have sufficient access to digital content and resources.	2.8	Occasionally
3. Teachers have sufficient access to office equipment and supplies such as copy machines, paper, pens, etc.	2.9	Occasionally
4. The physical environment of classrooms in this school supports teaching and learning.	3.3	Occasionally
5. The reliability and speed of Internet connections in this school are sufficient to support instructional practices.	2.9	Occasionally
Overall	3.3	Occasionally

Based on the data presented, items 1 and 2 got the same mean of 2.8 and items 3 and 5 got also same mean while item 4 got the mean of 3.3 with an overall description of occasionally respectively.

The Level of obstacles as perceived by the high school teachers in terms of Facilities and Resources got the overall mean of 3.3 with description of Occasionally.

Community Support and Involvement. Table 8 shows the Level of Obstacles as Perceived by the High School Teachers in terms of Community Support and Involvement.

Table 8. *The Level of Obstacles as Perceived by the High School Teachers in terms of Community Support and Involvement*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Parents/guardians are influential decision makers in this school.	2.3	Rarely
2. This school maintains clear, two-way communication with the community.	2.7	Occasionally
3. Parents/guardians support teachers, contributing to their success with students.	2.8	Occasionally
4. Community members support teachers, contributing to their success with students.	3.3	Occasionally
5. The community we serve is supportive of this school.	3.0	Occasionally
Overall	2.7	Occasionally

Based on the table presented, item 4 got the mean of 3.3; item 5 got the mean of 3.0 while item 3 got the mean of 2.8 and item 2 got the mean of 2.7 and got an overall description of occasionally respectively. Finally, item 1 got the lowest mean of 2.3 with description of rarely. The Level of obstacles as perceived by the high school teachers in terms of community support and involvement got an overall of 2.7 with description of occasionally.

Managing Student Conduct. Table 9 shows the Level of Obstacles as Perceived by the High School Teachers in terms of Managing Student Conduct.

Table 9. *The Level of Obstacles as Perceived by the High School Teachers in terms of Managing Student Conduct*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Students at this school understand expectations for their conduct.	2.7	Occasionally
2. Policies and procedures about student conduct are clearly understood by the faculty.	2.8	Occasionally
3. Students at this school follow rules of conduct.	2.9	Occasionally
4. School administrators consistently enforce rules for student conduct.	3.0	Occasionally
5. School administrators support teachers' efforts to maintain discipline in the classroom.	3.0	Occasionally
Overall	2.9	Occasionally

Based on the data presented, items 4 and 5 got the same mean of 3.0; items 3 got mean of 2.9; while item 2 got mean of 2.8 and item 1 got the mean of 2.7 with an overall descriptive equivalent of occasionally respectively. The Level of Obstacles as Perceived by the High School Teachers in terms of Managing Student Conduct got an overall mean of 2.9 with description of Occasionally.

School Leadership. Table 10 shows the Level of Obstacles as Perceived by the High School Teachers in terms of School Leadership.

Table 10. *The Level of Obstacles as Perceived by the High School Teachers in terms of School Leadership*

<i>Indicator</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. There is an atmosphere of trust and mutual respect in this school.	2.7	Occasionally
2. Teachers feel comfortable raising issues and concerns that are important to them.	2.8	Occasionally
3. The school leadership [2] consistently supports teachers.	2.8	Occasionally
4. Teachers receive feedback that can help them improve teaching.	3.0	Occasionally
5. The procedures for teacher evaluation are consistent.	3.1	Occasionally
Overall	2.9	Occasionally

Based on the data provided, item 1 got the lowest mean of 2.7; items 2 and 3 got the same mean of 2.8 it is followed by item 5 got the highest mean of 3.1, and item 4 got the mean of 3.0, with an overall descriptive equivalent of Occasionally respectively.

Teaching performance of the teachers in terms of IPCRF Rating. Table 11 presented the level of teaching performance of the teachers in terms of IPCRF Rating.

Table 11. *The Level of Teaching Performance of the Teachers in terms of IPCRF Rating*

<i>Metric</i>	<i>Value</i>
Mean Rating In IPCRF	4.5
Quality Index	Outstanding

The high mean rating of 4.5 in the IPCRF, coupled with an Outstanding quality index, implied that the teachers' teaching performance was exceptionally high.

This reflected that the teachers were highly effective in their roles, provided excellent education, and made a significant positive impact on their students' learning experiences. The outstanding quality index further underscored the exemplary standards of teaching that were maintained.

Significant Relationship Between the Level of coping strategies and the Level of performance of high school teachers. Table 12 presented the Significant Relationship Between the Level of coping strategies and the Level of performance of high school teachers.

Table 12. *Significant Relationship Between the Level of coping strategies and the Level of performance of high school teachers*

Variable		COP STRAT	OBSTACLE	IPCRF
1. COP STRAT	Pearson's r	—		
	p-value	—		
2. OBSTACLE	Pearson's r	0.168	—	
	p-value	0.013	—	
3. IPCRF	Pearson's r	0.040	0.033	—
	p-value	0.559	0.626	—

Table 12 presents Pearson's correlation coefficients (r) and their associated p -values for the relationships between three variables: COP STRAT (Coping Strategies), OBSTACLE, and IPCRF. The analysis reveals that there is a weak positive correlation between coping strategies and obstacles, with a Pearson's r of 0.168 and a p -value of 0.013, indicating statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that as coping strategies increase, obstacles slightly increase as well, although the relationship is weak.

In contrast, the correlation between coping strategies and IPCRF ratings is not significant, with a Pearson's r of 0.040 and a p -value of 0.559 ($p > 0.05$). This implies that coping strategies do not have a notable impact on the performance of teachers as measured by the IPCRF. Similarly, the correlation between obstacles and IPCRF ratings is also not significant, with a Pearson's r of 0.033 and a p -value of 0.626 ($p > 0.05$), indicating that obstacles do not significantly affect the performance of teachers according to the IPCRF.

Based on the data, there was no significant relationship between coping strategies and the performance of teachers, as indicated by a very weak and non-significant correlation ($r = 0.040$, $p = 0.559$). Similarly, there was no significant relationship between obstacles and the performance of teachers, with another very weak and non-significant correlation ($r = 0.033$, $p = 0.626$). These findings supported the statements that neither coping strategies nor obstacles had a notable impact on teachers' performance as measured by the IPCRF.

The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Seeking Support

The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Seeking Support had an overall mean of 3.3, with the descriptive equivalent of Occasionally. This finding suggested that teachers occasionally employed seeking support as a coping strategy when dealing with stress or challenges in their professional environment. The frequency of this behavior indicated that while seeking support was observed, it was not a predominant coping mechanism among the teachers surveyed.

The implication of these findings was significant for school administrators and policymakers. The results pointed to the need for strengthening support networks within the school environment, such as peer support groups, mentoring programs, and accessible counseling services. By fostering a culture that encourages seeking support and provides robust support structures, schools could help teachers more effectively manage stress and challenges. This, in turn, could lead to improved teacher morale, job satisfaction, and overall effectiveness, ultimately benefiting the entire educational community Rajesh et al., (2022) and Durksen et al., (2017).

As supported by McCallum (2021) and Tae et al. (2019) that seeking support played a role in the teachers' coping strategies, but it was not consistently relied upon. This occasional use might reflect a range of factors, including availability of support, cultural attitudes towards seeking help, or personal preferences for coping with stress independently. The occasional engagement in seeking support highlighted a potential area for intervention, suggesting that enhancing support systems and encouraging more frequent use of such strategies could be beneficial for teachers' overall well-being (Thakur et al., 2018; Burić & Kim, 2020).

The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Active Planning

The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Active Planning had an overall mean of 2.9, characterized as Occasionally. This result indicated that teachers occasionally utilized active planning as a coping strategy when confronted with challenges or stressors in their professional roles. The frequency of this behavior suggested that while active planning was recognized as a coping method, it was not consistently employed by the teachers surveyed.

The implication of these findings highlighted potential areas for support and development within educational institutions. School administrators and educational policymakers could consider strategies to promote and enhance active planning as a coping mechanism among teachers. As supported by Singha et al. (2020) that this might include providing training sessions on effective time management and stress management techniques, integrating planning tools into professional development programs, or fostering a supportive school culture that values proactive approaches to problem-solving Wal et al., (2019) and Stronge, (2018).

Furthermore, Sato and Loewen (2019) and Sherab and Schuelka (2019) also stated that these results underscored the importance of offering a diverse range of coping strategies and support mechanisms tailored to teachers' individual needs. By expanding the repertoire of coping skills available to educators and encouraging their proactive application, schools can better support teacher well-being and resilience. This approach not only enhances teachers' ability to manage stress effectively but also contributes to a more positive and productive school environment overall (Sunday-Piaroi, 2018; Zhao et al., 2019). It became clear that active planning played a role in teachers' coping strategies, albeit sporadically. Teachers may have employed active planning during certain situations where they felt the need to organize their tasks or approach challenges systematically. The occasional use of active planning could reflect varying

preferences in coping styles among educators, influenced by factors such as workload, time constraints, or individual coping preferences Acompanado, (2017).

The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Disengagement

The level of coping strategies in terms of disengagement had an overall mean of 3.0, which was characterized as occasionally. This result indicated that teachers occasionally employed disengagement as a coping strategy when faced with stress or challenges in their professional roles. The frequency of this behavior suggested that while disengagement was recognized as a coping mechanism, it was not consistently relied upon by the teachers surveyed.

The implication of these findings highlighted the importance of addressing the underlying causes of disengagement and promoting healthier coping mechanisms among teachers. School administrators and educational policymakers could consider strategies to mitigate stressors within the school environment, such as workload management, professional development on stress management techniques, and fostering a supportive organizational culture. Jomuad et al. (2021) and Darling-Hammond et al. (2018) also added that by reducing the triggers that lead to disengagement and promoting more effective coping strategies, schools could support teachers in maintaining higher levels of well-being and job satisfaction.

Furthermore, these results underscored the need for comprehensive support systems that encompass a variety of coping strategies tailored to teachers' individual needs. Educators may benefit from access to resources and training that promote adaptive coping skills, resilience-building techniques, and proactive approaches to managing stress Ujir et.al (2020). By enhancing teachers' ability to cope effectively with challenges, schools can cultivate a resilient and motivated workforce, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes and a positive school climate (Sjöman, 2018; Skolverket, 2020). Teachers may have resorted to disengagement during periods of high stress or when feeling overwhelmed, possibly withdrawing mentally or emotionally from stressful situations. The occasional use of disengagement could reflect varying coping preferences among educators, influenced by the nature of their work demands, personal resilience levels, or external stressors Renaldo (2023).

The level of Coping Strategies in terms of Suppression of Competing Behavior

The level of coping strategies in terms of suppression of competing behavior had an overall mean of 3.0, which was characterized as occasionally. This result indicated that teachers occasionally employed suppression of competing behavior as a coping strategy when confronted with stress or competing demands in their professional roles. The frequency of this behavior suggested that while suppression of competing behavior was recognized as a coping mechanism, it was not consistently relied upon by the teachers surveyed.

The implication of these findings underscored the importance of promoting adaptive coping strategies and stress management techniques among teachers. In addition, Guskey (2022), school administrators and educational policymakers could consider implementing interventions that enhance teachers' ability to effectively prioritize tasks, manage workload demands, and maintain focus amidst competing pressures. Providing training and support in time management, organizational skills, and mindfulness practices could empower educators to navigate stressors more effectively and sustain job performance over time Bell et.al (2019).

More so, these results highlighted the need for cultivating a supportive school climate that encourages open communication and collaboration among staff. By fostering an environment where teachers feel empowered to manage their workload and seek assistance when needed, schools can mitigate the impact of competing demands on teacher well-being and job satisfaction Lu and Xie, (2019) and Nordquist, (2017). This approach not only promotes resilience and adaptive coping strategies but also contributes to a positive work environment conducive to professional growth and educational success Steinberg and Kraft (2017).

The Level of obstacles as perceived by High school teachers in terms of Time

The Level of obstacles as perceived by high school teachers in terms of Time had an overall mean of 3.0, characterized as Occasionally. This result indicated that teachers occasionally perceived time-related obstacles as significant challenges in their professional roles. The frequency of this perception suggested that while time-related obstacles were recognized, they were not consistently identified as the primary barrier by the teachers surveyed.

The implication of these findings underscored the importance of addressing time-related obstacles to enhance teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction. School administrators and educational policymakers could consider strategies to alleviate time pressures, such as optimizing scheduling practices, providing additional planning periods, or streamlining administrative tasks. Humble et al., (2019) by reducing time-related barriers, schools can support teachers in focusing more on instructional quality, student engagement, and professional development, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes.

Furthermore, Dicke et al. (2018) and Lesener et al. (2019) these results highlighted the need for ongoing support and resources tailored to teachers' time management needs. Educators may benefit from training programs on efficient time management techniques, access to digital tools that streamline administrative tasks, or collaborative opportunities to share best practices for optimizing instructional time (Johnson et al., 2023; Al-Hadabi et al., 2020). By empowering teachers with the tools and support they need to manage their time effectively, schools can foster a productive and positive work environment conducive to professional growth and teacher well-being (Mathieu et al., 2019).

In addition, Gupta (2020) and Nielsen (2020) stated that high school teachers felt the strain of time when trying to implement new teaching strategies or participate in professional development. While they recognized the importance of staying current with educational trends and techniques, the time required to attend workshops or collaborate with colleagues was often hard to find. This limitation hindered their ability to innovate and improve their teaching practices, as the immediate demands of their schedules took precedence over long-term professional growth Ninan, (2020).

The Level of obstacles as perceived by High School teachers in terms of Facilities and Resources

The Level of obstacles as perceived by high school teachers in terms of Facilities and Resources had an overall mean of 3.3, characterized as Occasionally. This result indicated that teachers occasionally identified facilities and resources as significant obstacles in their professional roles. The frequency of this perception suggested that while these obstacles were recognized, they were not consistently viewed as primary barriers by the teachers surveyed.

The implication of these findings underscored the importance of addressing facilities and resource challenges to enhance teacher effectiveness and job satisfaction. School administrators and educational policymakers could consider strategies to improve infrastructure, upgrade equipment, and expand access to educational resources. Adamu et al. (2022) and Ahmodu and Sheu (2018) by investing in modernizing facilities, providing adequate supplies, and ensuring equitable distribution of resources across schools can support teachers in delivering high-quality education and meeting student needs more effectively (Robosa et al., 2021).

Furthermore, Harrigan et al., (2020) highlighted the need for proactive planning and resource management in educational institutions. Educators may benefit from collaborative efforts to identify and prioritize resource needs, advocating for necessary improvements, and leveraging community partnerships or grants to enhance school facilities. By addressing facilities and resource challenges systematically, schools can create a conducive learning environment that promotes teacher well-being, student achievement, and overall school success Barnes, (2018) and Agency, (2017).

The Level of obstacles as perceived by High School teachers in terms of community support and involvement

The Level of obstacles as perceived by high school teachers in terms of community support and involvement had an overall mean of 2.7, characterized as Occasionally. This result indicated that teachers occasionally identified community support and involvement as obstacles impacting their professional roles. The frequency of this perception suggested that while community support was acknowledged, it was not consistently seen as a significant barrier by the teachers surveyed.

The implication of these findings underscored the importance of fostering robust school-community partnerships to support teacher effectiveness and student achievement. School administrators and educational policymakers could consider strategies to enhance community engagement, build collaborative relationships with parents and local organizations, and promote active participation in school activities. Aperribai et al. (2020) strengthening ties between schools and their communities can create a supportive network that enriches educational experiences, expands resources, and cultivates a positive learning environment for students (Babarinde et al., 2023; Beard & Thomson, 2021).

Furthermore, these results highlighted the potential benefits of targeted initiatives to address barriers related to community support. Educators may benefit from professional development on community outreach strategies, cultural competency training, or initiatives that bridge communication gaps between schools and diverse community groups (Calao, 2020). By addressing challenges related to community support systematically, schools can promote inclusivity, equity, and holistic student development, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes and community well-being (Dziuban et al., 2018; Bryan et al., 2020).

The Level of Obstacles as Perceived by High School Teachers in terms of Managing Student Conduct

The Level of Obstacles Perceived by High School Teachers in terms of Managing Student Conduct had an overall mean of 2.9, characterized as Occasionally. This result indicated that teachers occasionally identified managing student conduct as a significant challenge in their professional roles. The frequency of this perception suggested that while managing student behavior was recognized as an obstacle, it was not consistently perceived as the predominant barrier by the teachers surveyed.

The implication of these findings underscored the importance of supporting teachers with effective classroom management strategies and resources. School administrators and educational policymakers could consider initiatives to enhance teacher training in behavior management techniques, provide mentoring or peer support networks for sharing best practices, and implement proactive measures to promote positive student behavior Alasmari and Althaqafi, (2021). By equipping teachers with the tools and support they need to manage student conduct effectively, schools can create a conducive learning environment that fosters academic achievement and student well-being Meador, (2019).

Furthermore, these results are highlighted by the study of Tus (2020), which shows the need for collaborative approaches between educators, students, and families to address behavior challenges comprehensively. Educators may benefit from fostering positive relationships with students, involving parents in behavior intervention plans, and implementing restorative practices to promote accountability and growth. By promoting a culture of respect, responsibility, and mutual support within schools, educators can mitigate barriers related to managing student conduct and cultivate a positive school climate conducive to learning and personal development

(Margot & Kettler, 2019; Cinelli et al., 2020).

The Level of Obstacles as Perceived by High School Teachers in terms of School Leadership

The Level of Obstacles as Perceived by High School Teachers in terms of School Leadership had an overall mean of 2.9, characterized as Occasionally. This result indicated that teachers occasionally identified school leadership as a significant obstacle in their professional roles. The frequency of this perception suggested that while challenges related to school leadership were acknowledged, they were not consistently perceived as the primary barrier by the teachers surveyed.

The implication of these findings underscored the importance of effective and supportive school leadership in fostering a positive work environment for educators. School administrators and educational policymakers could consider initiatives to enhance leadership training for administrators, promote transparent communication channels, and solicit feedback from teachers to improve leadership practices. By cultivating strong, collaborative leadership that values teacher input and supports professional growth, schools can enhance morale, retention rates, and overall job satisfaction among educators (Quirkos, 2020; Prastiawan et al., 2020).

Furthermore, Gilles et al. (2018) and Coquyt (2019) also highlighted the potential benefits of fostering a culture of shared leadership and empowerment within schools. Educators may benefit from opportunities to participate in decision-making processes, collaborate on school improvement initiatives, and contribute to shaping the educational vision and goals of the institution. By fostering a sense of ownership and inclusivity in school leadership practices, administrators can create a supportive and effective organizational culture that promotes student success and teacher well-being (Coquyt & Creasman, 2017).

The Level of Teaching Performance of the Teachers in terms of IPCRF Rating

The Level of Teaching Performance of the Teachers in terms of IPCRF Rating showed a high mean rating of 4.5 in the IPCRF, indicating an Outstanding quality index. This suggests that the teachers' teaching performance was exceptionally high, demonstrating their effectiveness and dedication in delivering quality education. The outstanding quality index further underscored the exemplary standards of teaching that were consistently maintained across various performance metrics.

The implication of these results emphasized the importance of recognizing and supporting effective teaching practices in educational settings. School administrators and policymakers could use these findings to identify and promote strategies that enhance teaching effectiveness, such as professional development opportunities, mentorship programs, and recognition for exemplary educators. The result of the study is supported by Camahalan et al. (2022) and Celesio (2020). By investing in teacher growth and fostering a culture of excellence, schools can cultivate a supportive environment that elevates teaching standards, enhances student achievement, and promotes overall educational success Hanan, (2023).

Interpreting these findings, it became evident that the high IPCRF ratings reflected the teachers' ability to meet and exceed educational standards, positively impacting student learning outcomes Dağlı and Baysal, (2017). Teachers demonstrated proficiency in instructional delivery, curriculum implementation, and student assessment, contributing significantly to their students' academic growth and development. The outstanding quality index highlighted the recognition of their exceptional teaching practices and their commitment to continuous improvement in educational excellence Shweta et al. (2024) and Fontaine et al. (2020).

Significant relationship between the Level of Coping strategies and the Level of Performance of High School Teachers

Based on the study's findings, significant relationship between the Level of coping strategies and the Level of performance of high school teachers. Based on the study's findings, it was concluded that there is no significant relationship between obstacles perceived by teachers and their performance, as measured by IPCRF ratings. The statistically insignificant correlation coefficient ($r = 0.033$, $p = 0.626$) between perceived obstacles and IPCRF ratings suggests that the challenges teachers perceive in their work environment do not notably impact their teaching performance. This finding implies that despite facing various obstacles such as administrative issues, resource limitations, or other challenges, teachers were able to maintain consistent performance levels as evaluated by the IPCRF.

The implication of these results highlights the resilience and professionalism of teachers in overcoming workplace challenges to maintain high standards of teaching effectiveness. School administrators and policymakers can use these findings to inform strategies aimed at supporting teachers in addressing obstacles effectively. This may include providing professional development on resilience-building techniques, enhancing support systems for teachers, and fostering a positive work environment that promotes teacher well-being and job satisfaction. Also, Malik (2020) and Hawati and Jerud (2020), by recognizing and addressing the diverse needs and challenges faced by educators, schools can create an environment conducive to sustained teaching excellence and positive student outcomes.

In addition, Arora (2020) and Salimzadeh et al. (2020), it became evident that while teachers may encounter obstacles in their professional roles, these challenges did not hinder their ability to effectively deliver instruction and meet performance standards. Teachers demonstrated resilience and adaptability in navigating potential barriers, possibly through effective coping mechanisms, professional skills, or support systems within the school environment. The lack of a significant relationship between perceived obstacles and IPCRF ratings suggests that other factors, such as teaching strategies, instructional methods, and personal dedication, may have a more substantial influence on teaching performance than perceived obstacles alone (Benevene et al., 2019 Tus, 2017).

Conclusions

The study highlighted that teachers employed coping strategies occasionally across various dimensions, such as Seeking Support, Active Planning, Disengagement, and Suppression of Competing Behavior. They perceived occasional challenges in Time, Facilities and Resources, Community Support and Involvement, Managing Student Conduct, and School Leadership. Despite these perceived obstacles, teachers' performance, evaluated through IPCRF ratings, consistently demonstrated high effectiveness in delivering quality education and positively impacting student learning. The findings underscored the robust standards of teaching maintained by teachers, as reflected in the outstanding quality index. Moreover, the study confirmed no significant correlation between coping strategies or perceived obstacles and teacher performance, indicating that these factors did not predict variations in teacher performance outcomes as assessed by IPCRF ratings.

Students were encouraged to engage in understanding teacher challenges and support mechanisms. An environment was fostered where students appreciated the efforts of teachers and their dedication to effective teaching practices.

For School Administration, resources were strategically allocated to address specific obstacles perceived by teachers, such as improving facilities and resources, enhancing community support and involvement, and refining school leadership practices. Ongoing professional development was supported to reinforce effective teaching strategies.

For the teachers, continuous training and support were provided on coping strategies and stress management. A collaborative culture was fostered where teachers shared effective practices and supported each other in managing workload and challenges.

Stakeholders, including educational policymakers, community leaders, and business partners, were engaged in initiatives supporting teacher well-being and educational excellence. Advocacy efforts focused on policies prioritizing teacher support and professional growth.

Partnerships with parents were fostered to understand and support teachers' efforts. Parental involvement was encouraged in school activities and initiatives contributing to a positive learning environment. Efforts were made to educate parents about teachers' challenges and the importance of their role in supporting effective education practices. These recommendations aimed to create a supportive ecosystem where teachers could thrive professionally, leading to improved student outcomes and overall school effectiveness.

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